

The Alan Turing Institute

The background of the slide is a photograph of industrial machinery, likely a power plant or refinery. It features large, horizontal pipes at the top, several vertical cylindrical vessels in the middle, and a row of electrical control cabinets at the bottom. A white diagonal shape cuts across the image from the top-left towards the bottom-right, creating a space for text.

Data Study Group

Final Report:

Centre for Postdoctoral
Development in
Infrastructure, Cities,
and Energy (C-DICE)

A Cost-Effective Roadmap for
Achieving Net Zero Carbon
Emissions by 2050

**27 January 2025 -
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1 Executive Summary

Achieving a net zero energy system requires strategic planning of infrastructure transitions. This study presents a [software tool](#) that generates optimal transition plans for the UK power sector. Given a set of predefined decarbonisation milestones, the tool constructs a roadmap that specifies which power plants should be built, expanded, repurposed, or decommissioned (retired). This roadmap is designed to gradually transform the existing energy system, ensuring milestones are met at a minimal cost (see Appendix B).

1.1 Challenge Overview and Objective

This report presents an optimisation framework for repurposing and decommissioning energy assets to support the UK's Net Zero 2050 target. This challenge, introduced by the Centre for Postdoctoral Development in Infrastructure, Cities, and Energy (C-DICE), focuses on developing a cost-effective roadmap for transitioning the UK power sector from non-renewable energy sources (e.g., coal, oil, gas, and biomass) to renewable energy (e.g., wind, solar, hydro, and nuclear).

The objective is to determine the lowest-cost set of projects that collectively achieve the 2050 Net Zero target through the following intervention types:

- Decommission non-renewable power plants (e.g., dismantling a coal-fired power station and restoring the site).
- Repurpose non-renewable plants into renewable energy plants (e.g., converting a coal plant to run on sustainably sourced biomass).
- Upgrade existing renewable energy plants (e.g., upgrading older wind turbines with modern models to increase efficiency).

We apply linear optimisation to support long-term strategic decision-making over a 25-year period, with solutions optimised at 5-year intervals.

1.2 Data Overview

The optimisation model integrates two publicly available datasets:

- ESME (Energy System Modeling Environment) Scenarios (see Section 3.1.1):

Defines the generation capacity milestones for the different power sources from 2010 to 2050 in five-year increments under two scenarios:

- Clockwork scenario for centralised energy planning
- Patchwork scenario for regional energy transitions
- JRC (Joint Research Centre) Powerplant Database (see Section 3.1.2):
Contains global power plant data, including fuel types, capacities, operational status, and emissions.

In addition, a private document provided by C-DICE containing the costs of executing repurposing, decarbonisation and construction projects. This document was compiled using publicly available data.

1.3 Method

The problem is formulated as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) model using cost as the objective function (see Section 5.1). The model incorporates soft constraints to reflect flexibility in meeting the milestones provided. `pyomo` is the tool employed to model and optimise the problem (see Section 5.2). Finally, a preliminary exploration using a Markov Decision Process (MDP) framework is included to assess how uncertainty and sequential decision-making could enhance the model's realism (see Section 5.3).

1.4 Findings and implications

Results show that the optimisation framework consistently identifies feasible and cost-effective transition pathways that meet capacity targets within scenario constraints. These findings suggest that, with accurate input data and scenario specifications, operational research methods can provide reliable guidance for large-scale infrastructure planning.

Incorporating Markov Decision Process (MDP) methods offers a promising direction to capture uncertainty in demand, costs, and policy, enabling more adaptive and robust decision-making. This would yield a more realistic and adaptive representation of the energy transition problem, enabling more robust and informed decision-making in dynamic real-world contexts.

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

This challenge was set by the Centre for Postdoctoral Development in Infrastructure, Cities, and Energy (C-DICE), an organisation devoted to empowering researchers with the essential skills and comprehensive knowledge required to confront one of the most critical global issues of our time: the attainment of net zero carbon emissions by the year 2050.

Energy production is the largest contributor to greenhouse gas emissions globally, accounting for approximately 73% of total emissions, with the majority originating from the combustion of fossil fuels for electricity and heat [6]. Generating energy from coal, oil, and natural gas, releases significant amounts of carbon dioxide, while renewable sources such as wind, solar, and hydroelectric power generate electricity with little to no direct emissions. Redesigning the UK's energy generation infrastructure is therefore essential to reducing the national carbon footprint.

The challenge seeks to develop innovative solutions for designing a concrete sequence of projects to transform the UK's power plants towards the Net Zero 2050 target. This roadmap must ensure reliable energy supply year-round, regardless of time of day or weather conditions. Fortunately, the ESME model has already determined the required energy mix and capacity targets needed to meet future demand. Therefore, our task is to schedule projects to ensure that the five-year milestones outlined in the ESME scenarios are met.

C-DICE intends to use this roadmap to estimate the number and types of projects required over time, as well as the associated workforce demand. These insights will help inform decisions on how many postdoctoral researchers should be trained for key roles in the energy transition, such as project management.

2.2 Objectives

This challenge is centred on developing a comprehensive and strategic roadmap for the repurposing, decommissioning, and upgrading of energy assets, aimed at significantly enhancing their effectiveness in contributing to the UK's goal of achieving Net Zero carbon emissions by 2050 [15].

To accomplish this, we will employ different optimisation techniques to analyse

and evaluate various scenarios. This will facilitate the identification of the most cost-effective strategies tailored to the unique characteristics of different energy assets.

Furthermore, our approach will consider the five-year milestones outlined by the Energy System Modelling Environment (ESME). By aligning our strategies with these milestones, we ensure that the roadmap meets immediate objectives and supports long-term sustainability and efficiency in the energy sector. This detailed analysis will encompass factors such as economic viability, environmental impacts, regulatory requirements, and technological advancements, ultimately leading to a robust and adaptable plan for the future of energy in the UK.

3 Data overview

This study draws upon three publicly available data sources that inform strategic capacity targets and existing infrastructure constraints: i) the ESME scenarios [2, 3] that describe the desired trajectory in transitioning to net zero energy production, ii) the global powerplant database [13], and iii) the JRC powerplant database [7]. The objective is to propose actions on the UK powerplants that minimise the financial cost while meeting as closely as possible the ESME Net Zero milestones. Although the JRC and Global Power Plant datasets could be merged for greater coverage, inconsistencies between them and the short project timeframe led us to focus solely on the JRC dataset. Extending our work to incorporate the global dataset is a possibility for future work.

3.1 Dataset description

3.1.1 ESME

The Energy System Modelling Environment (ESME) is a national-level least-cost optimisation tool developed by the Energy Technologies Institute (ETI). It explores technology options for a carbon-constrained energy system while considering factors like peak demand and infrastructure across power, transport, buildings, and industry, in the following two scenarios:

- **Clockwork:** with a well-coordinated centrally planned long-term energy infrastructure, and

- **Patchwork:** with a series of distinct regional energy strategies (eventually integrated by the government)

For each scenario, ESME provides a sequence of milestones that guide the UK’s progress toward Net Zero by 2050. Capacity milestones are specified at five-year intervals from 2010 to 2050 and are visualised in Figure 1 (1st version 4.0).

Figure 1: Milestones ESME has designed to achieve Net Zero by 2050.

Our optimisation model focuses specifically on the “Electricity Generation Capacity” milestones, which prescribe capacities for various energy technologies at five-year intervals, for example, the solar energy capacity the UK must have in 2035. We aim to generate a sequence of projects that meets the milestones provided by any given scenario. First, a solution for the Clockwork scenario will be generated, and then, the approach will be generalised to Patchwork or any other scenario.

For each scenario, these milestones are provided in a *xlsx* file that includes 22 different types of data, with a stacked histogram visualisation and an accompanying table for each type. The table, which can be visualised in Figure 1, has a column for each of the different energy sources considered and nine columns with numerical

¹see <https://es.catapult.org.uk/brochures/esme-data-references-book> for more

data, representing the energy capacity the UK must have of each energy source during each five-year step between 2010 and 2050.

Minor naming inconsistencies exist between the Clockwork and Patchwork scenarios, but being aware of this suffices to avoid problems when processing the data (see Appendix A).

3.1.2 European Commission’s Joint Research Centre

To optimise the transition to meet future ESME milestone, we require data for existing UK infrastructure. This is sourced from the JRC Open Power Plant Database, maintained by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre [7], which was published in July 2019 (version 1.0). This dataset contains four tables in csv format:

1. Unit table: characteristics of the individual power plant units
2. Linkage table: mapping of the keys and id codes for several datasets
3. Performance table: indicators for a subset of units
4. Temporal table: yearly statistics for a subset of units

Of the four available tables, the Unit table is the most relevant, as it contains capacity, technology type, and operational status for each power plant. Moreover, it contains other information such as location and construction date that might be beneficial to take into account in future works. This information is detailed in Table 1, and its information is processed as described in Section 4.3.

3.2 Data quality

Data quality is assessed using the framework proposed by [11], which evaluates five dimensions:

- **Appropriateness:** Was the data relevant to the questions posed?
- **Readiness:** Is the data complete, is relevant metadata available, and is there sufficient data documentation?
- **Reliability / Bias:** To what extent do the data accurately represent the population or phenomenon? Are there systematic data collection errors or distortions?

Field	SQL Type	Description
eic_p	varchar(20)	EIC (Energy Identification Code) for the producing unit
eic_g	varchar(20)	EIC (Energy Identification Code) for the generation unit
name_p	text	Production unit name
name_g	text	Generating unit name
capacity_p	float	Production unit capacity, net (MW)
capacity_g	float	Generating unit capacity, net (MW)
type_g	text	ENTSO-E classification for the generation unit
lat	float	Latitude (WGS84)
lon	float	Longitude in the range -180, 180 (WGS84)
country	varchar(40)	Name of the country
NUTS2	text	NUTS2 code according to the NUTS 2016 definition
status_g	text	Status of the generating unit
year_commissioned	int	Year of commissioning
year_decommissioned	int	Year of decommissioning

Table 1: JRC Open Units Table

- **Sensitivity: Was the data private or confidential?** Data sensitivity refers to the level of confidentiality and privacy associated with specific types of data. It indicates the degree to which the data is considered private, personal, or valuable, requiring enhanced protection
- **Sufficiency:** Was the amount of data enough?

Each dimension can be assessed as Insufficient, Developing, Functional, or Optimal (see Section 4 of [11] for more details on the assessment matrix).

3.2.1 ESME Data Quality

Dimension	Insufficient	Developing	Functional	Optimal
Appropriateness				✓
Readiness			✓	
Reliability/Bias			✓	
Sensitivity				✓
Sufficiency		✓		

Table 2: Quality assessment of ESME scenarios data

- **Appropriateness: Optimal** — The ESME dataset provides long-term energy capacity milestones directly aligned with our planning objectives, making it highly relevant.
- **Readiness: Functional** — The data is well-organized with structured tables and visualizations. However, different scenarios include different power sources, so some details have to be taken into account before developing a tool that works for every scenario.
- **Reliability/Bias: Functional** — Produced by trusted institutions (ETI and Energy Systems Catapult), but based on projections rather than empirical data, introducing potential modeling bias.
- **Sensitivity: Optimal** — All information is fully aggregated and publicly available; no personal or sensitive data is included.

- **Sufficiency: Developing** — The dataset provides system-wide guidance but lacks regional, plant-level, or operational details necessary for infrastructure-specific modelling.

3.2.2 JRC Data Quality

Dimension	Insufficient	Developing	Functional	Optimal
Appropriateness			✓	
Readiness			✓	
Reliability/Bias			✓	
Sensitivity				✓
Sufficiency		✓		

Table 3: Quality assessment of JRC Open Units Table

- **Appropriateness: Functional** — The dataset provides detailed plant-level data essential for our model but does not directly align with the power sources breakdown in the ESME scenarios, requiring preprocessing.
- **Readiness: Functional** — Delivered in a clean CSV format with key fields and adequate documentation. Some entries have missing or outdated values, though the structure remains usable.
- **Reliability/Bias: Functional** — Compiled by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre, with data aggregated from various national and international sources. Some inconsistencies and temporal gaps exist.
- **Sensitivity: Optimal** — The dataset is entirely public and does not include personal or proprietary information.
- **Sufficiency: Developing** — While extensive, it lacks records and operational cost details, which limits its use without augmentation from other sources.

3.3 Data provided by C-DICE and Missing data

To achieve our goal of minimising the costs of satisfying the milestones given by the ESME scenarios (or any other scenario), we needed more information, some

of which was provided by C-DICE and that was complemented with information on the internet.

3.3.1 Costs of projects

Table 4 summarises the assumed costs and durations (in millions of GBP per MW and work years, respectively) for each category of infrastructure intervention.

Action	Technology	Duration	Cost
Upgrade	Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	1.0	10.42112
	Nuclear	1.0	5.11296
	Wind Offshore	1.0	3.78112
	Wind Onshore	1.0	0.93568
Decommission	Fossil Hard coal	5.0	0.85232
	Fossil Oil	1.0	0.37184
	Fossil Gas	1.0	0.37184
	Biomass	1.0	0.70656
Repurpose	Fossil Hard coal → Biomass	5.0	4.38512
	Fossil Hard coal → Nuclear	5.0	4.38512
	Fossil Oil → Biomass	5.0	3.90464
Build	Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	5.0	13.0264
	Nuclear	5.0	6.3912
	Wind Offshore	3.0	4.7264
	Wind Onshore	3.0	1.1696

Table 4: Duration (work years) and cost (millions of GBP per MW) of different interventions

Construction costs for new power plants are based on maximum capital expenditure (CAPEX) figures reported by the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA, 2022) and the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL, 2022). To maintain consistency across project types, derived costs for repurposing, upgrading, and

decommissioning are calculated using predefined formulas based on construction cost. Specifically, repurposing costs are defined as the sum of the associated decommissioning and new construction costs. Upgrading costs are assumed to be 80% of construction costs, while decommissioning costs are set at 20%. These standardised calculations provide a structured methodology for evaluating the financial implications of power plant development, ensuring transparency and consistency in cost across different scenarios.

- Repurposing Cost = Decommissioning Cost + Construction Cost
- Upgrading Cost = $0.8 \times$ Construction Cost
- Decommissioning Cost = $0.2 \times$ Construction Cost
- Exchange rate: 1 USD = 0.8 GBP

3.3.2 Other data needed

In addition to cost estimates, several other modelling assumptions are required to complete the optimisation framework, including project durations, capacity adjustments, and penalty terms.

In this section we cover how this data was imputed or determined, providing more accurate data would improve the quality of the result:

1. **Upgrading percentage:** How much the capacity of a renewable power plant changes after upgrading. We assume that upgrading increases plant's capacity by a fixed 50%, i.e., a plant rated at 1000 MW would be upgraded to 1500 MW after upgrading.
2. **Penalties** are applied when capacity shortfalls occur relative to the ESME milestones. These penalties, expressed in millions of GBP per MW, are informed by global benchmarks for carbon pricing.
3. **Intervention durations**, measured in work years, are estimated and reported in Table 4. These values serve as approximations due to the lack of real-world data.

4 Approach

4.1 Research Questions

This study aims to develop a framework that generates an optimal roadmap for decommissioning and repurposing fossil-fuel power plants, while meeting net zero targets by 2050. The framework should minimise costs, meet energy demand, and enforce capacity constraints for different energy sources over multiple time periods.

In addition, we explore how the uncertainty that arises from future demand, costs, or project duration can be integrated into the planning process.

4.2 Scientific Approach: Mixed Integer Linear Optimisation

Optimisation is a systematic method for identifying values of decision variables that maximise or minimise an objective function, subject to a set of constraints [12]. This technology has wide range of applications, including route planning, supply chain optimisation, and infrastructure scheduling.

Optimisation aims to enhance performance, improve efficiency, and enable informed decision-making that aligns with strategic objectives while taking into account resource availability, budget limitations, and other restrictions.

For example, it can be used to determine the optimal mix of products a factory should produce in order to maximise profit, given limitations in raw materials, labour, and production capacity.

Linear Programming (LP) is a widely used framework for solving optimisation problems where both the objective function and constraints are linear. It supports efficient optimisation even with thousands of continuous variables [4]

Mixed-Integer Linear Programming is a framework that under the same conditions of Linear Programming, allows decision variables that only take discrete values. The inclusion of integer variables enables a broader class of problems to be modelled, but increases computational complexity, and solving problems with thousands of decision variables becomes impossible.

For this case study, a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model is appropriate, as it allows binary variables to represent discrete project decisions

(e.g., whether or not to execute a specific intervention). This methodology has already been applied to the optimal energy system design of Zero Energy Buildings [8].

4.3 Data Preprocessing

Our analysis integrates data from two sources: the ESME scenario datasets and the JRC Open Power Plants dataset. Because these datasets differ in format and coverage, preprocessing is required to make their structure consistent for analysis. Let us start by describing the actions we take on the JRC dataset (JRC Open Units Table):

1. Since the JRC dataset includes global power plants, we filter the data to retain only those located in the United Kingdom. The filtered dataset is exported as a .csv file.
2. We focus on power plant capacity, the maximum amount of energy that a power plant can produce. This measure is given by `capacity_p` in Table 1, in units of MW. This metric is prioritised because most of the available power plants in the dataset include this information.
3. To identify each powerplant, we need its energy identification code (`eic_p` in Table 1). To ensure unique power plants, duplicates were removed based on its identification code.
4. We keep only the commissioned power plants: those in which `status_g` in Table 1 is commissioned.

Because the JRC dataset uses broader technology categories, we map the more granular ESME technology types to the JRC `type_g` field. This mapping is shown in Table 5. To support the mapping, we apply Word2Vec word embeddings [9, 10], which learns vector representations of words by predicting context words from a target word (Skip-gram) or predicting a target word from its context (CBOW). The result consists of dense word embeddings where similar words have closer vectors, capturing semantic and syntactic relationships.

Several limitations affect the completeness of the dataset. Notably, the JRC data lacks entries for solar power, there is no JRC-equivalent for Hydro Pumped Storage, and some ESME technologies remain unmapped. Consequently, these technologies are excluded from this study.

JRC	Clockwork Technologies	Patchwork Technologies
Fossil Gas	CCGT, CCGT with CCS, CCGT with CCS - 99% CCR, Gas Macro CHP, OCGT	CCGT, CCGT with CCS, Gas Macro CHP, OCGT
Nuclear	Nuclear (Gen III), Nuclear (Legacy), Nuclear (SMR CHP)	Nuclear (Gen III), Nuclear (Gen IV), Nuclear (Legacy), Nuclear (SMR CHP NE), Nuclear (SMR CHPNW), Nuclear (SMR CHP SW), Nuclear (SMR Elec only)
Fossil Hard Coal	IGCC Coal with CCS - 99% CCR, PC Coal	IGCC Coal with CCS, PC Coal
Wind Onshore	Onshore Wind	Onshore Wind
Hydro Run-of-river and Poundage (RoRP)	Hydro Power	Hydro Power
Wind Offshore	Offshore Wind (fixed), Offshore Wind (floating)	Offshore Wind (fixed), Offshore Wind (floating)
Biomass	Anaerobic Digestion CHP Plant, Biomass Fired Generation, Converted Biomass Plant (Drax), Incineration of Waste, Waste Gasification, Waste Gasification with CCS	Anaerobic Digestion CHP Plant, Biomass Fired Generation, Biomass Macro CHP, Converted Biomass Plant (Drax), IGCC Biomass with CCS, Incineration of Waste, Waste Gasification, Waste Gasification with CCS
Fossil Oil	Oil Fired Generation	Oil Fired Generation
Uncategorized	H2 Turbine, Interconnector Benelux-Germany (Electricity), Interconnector France (Electricity), Interconnector Ireland (Electricity), Interconnector Nordel (Electricity), Solar PV (Domestic), Solar PV (Farm), Tidal Stream	Geothermal Plant (EGS) Electricity & Heat, H2 Micro CHP - Space Heat, H2 Turbine, Interconnector Benelux-Germany (Electricity), Interconnector France (Electricity), Interconnector Ireland (Electricity), Interconnector Nordel (Electricity), Solar PV (Domestic), Solar PV (Farm), Tidal Stream

Table 5: Mapping of energy technologies from Clockwork and Patchwork Scenarios, to JRC type_g

After establishing the mapping between ESME and JRC technology types given in Table 5, we derive the capacity demand per timestep from the ESME scenarios and convert it from gigawatts (GW) to megawatts (MW) for internal consistency. The resulting demands are shown in Tables 6 for the clockwork and 7 for the patchwork scenario.

	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Biomass	0	4	7	7	5	5	3	5	2
Fossil Gas	38	39	36	35	26	23	17	10	6
Fossil Hard coal	27	18	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fossil Oil	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hydro RoRP	2	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	3
Nuclear	10	9	9	7	9	12	21	29	37
Wind Offshore	1	5	15	18	18	18	18	21	34
Wind Onshore	4	19	22	22	20	21	21	20	20
Total Demand	90	109	122	113	105	108	114	129	153

Table 6: The demand in GW for the clockwork ESME scenario, after mapping the ESME technologies to the JRC types.

	2010	2015	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Biomass	0	4	7	7	5	5	3	5	2
Fossil Gas	38	39	36	35	26	23	17	10	6
Fossil Hard coal	27	18	9	0	0	0	0	0	0
Fossil Oil	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hydro RoRP	2	1	1	1	2	3	3	3	3
Nuclear	10	9	9	7	9	12	21	29	37
Wind Offshore	1	5	15	18	18	18	18	21	34
Wind Onshore	4	19	22	22	20	21	21	20	20
Total Demand	90	109	122	113	105	108	114	129	153

Table 7: The demand in GW for the patchwork ESME scenario, after mapping the ESME technologies to the JRC types.

5 Mathematical Formulations of the Problem

During the Data Science Study Group, participants explored different ways to formalise the energy transition planning problem. One group focused on developing a general mathematical formulation to capture the full complexity of the system (see Section 5.1). Another group worked on a simplified but implementable model that could be solved within the project’s time constraints (see Section 5.2). Additionally, some participants explored a stochastic variant based on Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) to account for uncertainty in project execution (see Section 5.3).

This section presents all three approaches. Among them, the implemented formulation described in Section 5.2 is the most relevant for the remainder of the

report, as it is further analysed in Section 6.

5.1 General Theoretical Formulation

To begin, we consider a simplified version of the problem.

Problem Specification Imagine there are existing p non-renewable plants and q renewable plants in 2025, their capacities Cap are $\text{Cap}_1^n, \text{Cap}_2^n, \dots, \text{Cap}_p^n$ and $\text{Cap}_1^r, \text{Cap}_2^r, \dots, \text{Cap}_q^r$, where r stands for renewable and n for non-renewable. The total target capacities for each type of plants in 2030 (the next time period) are X and Y . The non-renewable plants can be decommissioned or repurposed to renewable ones, where renewable plants can be upgraded (adding capacity to the original plants) or created (adding new plants). What are the optimal actions to consider for each power plant such that the capacities target are met in the most cost-efficient way?

Theoretical Mathematical Formulation Assumptions

Initial power plants' capacity Costs of projects:

- C_r : Cost per MW to add new renewable capacity (£/MW)
- C_n : Cost per MW to decommission non-renewable capacity (£/MW)
- C_{nr} : Cost per MW to repurpose non-renewable to renewable (£/MW)
- $D_{p,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if non-renewable plant p is decommissioned at time t , 0 otherwise.
- $R_{p,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if non-renewable plant p is repurposed to renewable at time t , 0 otherwise.

Target Capacity (2030)

- $\text{Target}_n = x$ MW
- $\text{Target}_r = y$ MW

Decision Variables

- Decommission Variables
 - Non-renewables: $\text{Decommission}_i^n \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$

- Renewables: $\text{Decommission}_i^r \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, q\}$
- Repurpose Variables from Non-renewable to renewable:
 - $\text{Repurpose}_i^n \in \{0, 1\}$, $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$
- Create Variables:
 - $\text{Create}_j^r \in \mathbb{Z}$: The number of MW of the new renewable plant j , j could be added as many as we might need.

Objective Function (Minimise Costs)

$\min(C_{\text{Decommission}} + C_{\text{Repurpose}} + C_{\text{Create}})$ where

- Decommission cost: $C_{\text{Decommission}} = C_n \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n \text{Decommission}_i^n$
- Repurpose cost: $C_{\text{Repurpose}} = C_{n2r} \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n \text{Repurpose}_i^n$
- Create cost: $C_{\text{Create}} = C_r \sum_j \text{Create}_j^r$

Constraints

Binary Constraints:

$$\text{Repurpose}, \text{Decommission} \in \{0, 1\}$$

Non-negativity constraints:

$$\text{Create}_j^r \geq 0, \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, q\}$$

One project per plant:

$$\text{Repurpose}_i^n + \text{Decommission}_i^n \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$$

Non-renewable Capacity Balance (with 10% margin):

$$0.9 \cdot \text{Target}_n \leq \sum_i^p \text{Cap}_i^n (1 - \text{Decommission}_i^n - \text{Repurpose}_i^n) \leq 1.1 \cdot \text{Target}_n$$

Energy Demand Constraint:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_t = & \sum_i^p \text{Cap}_i^n (1 - \text{Decommission}_i^n - \text{Repurpose}_i^n) \\
 & + \sum_j \text{Cap}_j^r (1 - \text{Decommission}_j^r) \\
 & + \sum_k \text{Create}_k^r \\
 & \geq D_t
 \end{aligned}$$

Repurpose Once Constraint: For only one time step

$$\text{Repurpose}_i^n \leq 1, \forall I \in (1, \dots, p)$$

for multiple time steps, we can sum over time

$$\sum_t \text{Repurpose}_i^n \leq 1, \forall I \in (1, \dots, p)$$

Renewable Capacity Balance:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 0.9 \cdot \text{Target}_r \\
 & \leq \sum_i^p \text{Cap}_i^n \text{Repurpose}_i^n \\
 & \quad + \sum_i^q \text{Cap}_i^r (1 - \text{Decommission}_i^r) \\
 & \quad + \sum_j \text{Create}_j^r \\
 & \leq 1.1 \cdot \text{Target}_r
 \end{aligned}$$

Standard Form of Mixed Integer Programming (MIP)

$$\min \quad C_n \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n x_i + C_{n2r} \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n x_{p+i} + C_r^+ \sum_{j=1}^m x_{2p+q+j},$$

s.t.

$$\begin{aligned} x_i + x_{p+i} &\leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, p \\ - \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n (1 - x_i - x_{p+i}) &\leq 0.9 \cdot \text{Target}_n \\ \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n (1 - x_i - x_{p+i}) &\leq 1.1 \cdot \text{Target}_n \\ \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n (1 - x_i - x_{p+i}) &\leq 1.1 \cdot \text{Target}_n \\ - \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n x_{p+i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \text{Cap}_i^r (1 - x_{2p+i}) + \sum_{j=1}^m x_{2p+q+j} &\leq 0.9 \cdot \text{Target}_r \\ \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Cap}_i^n x_{p+i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \text{Cap}_i^r (1 - x_{2p+i}) + \sum_{j=1}^m x_{2p+q+j} &\leq 1.1 \cdot \text{Target}_r, \\ x_i &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \\ x_{p+i} &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, p, \\ x_{2p+i} &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, q, \\ x_{2p+q+j} &\in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \end{aligned}$$

Here, x_i represents the decommissioning of non-renewable capacity, x_{p+i} denotes the repurposing of non-renewable capacity into renewable, x_{2p+i} corresponds to the decommissioning of renewable capacity, and x_{2p+q+j} signifies the creation of new renewable capacity.

5.2 Implementation of a MIP

The approach optimises the solution to a MIP problem over multiple time steps. Since our problem requires finding the optimal solution over a **25-year period**, we determine the optimal solution at **five-year intervals** based on the given scenario. To achieve this, we formulate the problem as a multi-step mixed integer programming model, ensuring a structured approach to long-term decision-making.

Since real-world transitions cannot always strictly follow target trajectories, we introduce **soft constraints** with **penalties** to allow deviations while ensuring the system remains feasible.

Penalty: A penalty in optimisation represents a cost imposed on constraint violations. It allows slight deviations from strict targets while discouraging excessive violations by adding a proportional cost to the objective function.

Mathematical Formulation used in the implementation Indices

To structure the optimisation problem, we define the following indices:

- $i \in \text{NP}$ represents non-renewable power plants. In our example, we have $\text{NP} = \{\text{Fossil Hard Coal, Oil, Fossil, Gas, Nuclear}\}$
- $j \in \text{RP}$ represents the renewable plants. In our example, we have $\text{RP} = \{\text{WindOffshore, WindOnshore, Hydro, Solar, etc.}\}$
- $t \in T$ denotes time periods (in years). In our case $T = \{2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, 2050\}$

Assumptions and Parameters

The model incorporates various cost parameters associated with power plant capacity changes, including cost of decommission, cost of repurpose, cost of building a new power plant and cost of upgrading existing power plant. For simplicity, we can use the following notation:

- C_{decomm}^i : cost of decommissioning each non-renewable plant by type (£/MW)
- C_{repurp}^i : cost per MW of repurposing each power plant of source s .
- C_{build}^j : Cost per MW to build new renewable Capacity for each renewable plant by type.(£/MW)
- $C_{enhance}^j$: Cost per MW to enhance each renewable capacity of existing plants.(£/MW)

As each type of non-renewable and renewable plants (e.g. coal, biomass, hydro, etc.) can be associated with different costs, to expand, we can further define the

cost function as:

$$cost(x) = \begin{cases} C_{decomm}^{coal}, & \text{if } x \in NP_{coal}, \\ \vdots & \\ C_{decomm}^{biomass}, & \text{if } x \in NP_{biomass}, \\ C_{build}^{coal}, & \text{if } x \in NP_{coal} \\ \vdots & \\ C_{repurp}^{coal2nuclear}, & \text{if } x \in NP_{coal}, \\ \vdots & \\ C_{enhance}^{hydro}, & \text{if } x \in RP_{hydro}. \end{cases}$$

Decision Variables

The model also includes binary decision variables

- $decom_{i,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if non-renewable plant i of source s is decommissioned at time t , 0 otherwise.
- $repurpose_{i,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if non-renewable plant i is repurposed to renewable at time t , 0 otherwise.
- $Create_t \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$: new renewable Capacity (MW) added in period t .
- $Cap_{e,t} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$: n Capacity (MW) added in existing renewable plant in period t
- $Enhance_{j,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if Capacity of any renewable plant has to be enhanced or not at time t .
- $Add_{j,t}$: Binary decision variable, 1 if new plant should be created at time t .

Additional parameters include

- $Cap_i = \{Cap_1, \dots, Cap_{NP}\}$: Initial Capacities of non-renewable plants.(MW)
- $Cap_j = \{Cap_1, \dots, Cap_{RP}\}$: Initial Capacities of renewable plants. (MW)
- $Energy_{demand,t}$ is energy demand per time period t

Target Capacities for 2050

The optimisation problem aims to achieve specific energy capacity targets by 2050:

- Target_n (MW)
- Target (MW)

State Variables and Penalties

To represent capacity at each time step:

- **Non-renewable capacity at time t :** Cap_i, t , which denotes the total capacity of non-renewable plants.
- **Renewable capacity at time for specific source t :** $Cap_{j,t}$, which denotes the total capacity of renewable plants.

Slack variables and penalties are introduced to handle soft constraints

- $s_{i,t}, s_{j,t}, s_t^d$ represent how much constraints are violated regarding non-renewable, renewable and total energy demand.
- $p_{i,t}, p_{j,t}, p_t^d$ represent the cost of violating each constraint.

The penalty function is defined as Penalty = violation cost · slack variable, where

- $p_t s_t$ penalises deviation from non-renewable energy target.
- $p_t s_t$ penalises deviation from renewable energy target.
- $p_t^d s_t^d$ penalises deviation from total energy target.

Objective Function: Minimising Costs

The objective function seeks to minimise the total cost associated with energy transitions

$$\min \sum_{i \in T} \left[\sum_{i \in NP} C_{repurp,s} Cap_i repurp_{i,t} + \sum_{i \in NP} C_{decomm,i} Cap_i decomm_{i,t} + C_{Create,t} Add_{j,t} + \sum_{j \in RP} C_{build,j} Cap_{e,t} Enhance_{j,t} + p_t \cdot s_t + p_t \cdot s_t + p_t^d \cdot s_t^d \right] \quad (1)$$

Capacity Evolution Over Time

The capacity of power plants evolves according to the following constraints, namely

- Non-renewable capacity dynamics:

$$\text{Cap}_{t+1} = \text{Cap}_t - \sum_{i \in \text{NP}} \text{Cap}_i (\text{decomm}_{i,t} + \text{repurp}_{i,t}), \forall t \in T$$

- Renewable capacity dynamics:

$$\text{Cap}_{j,t+1} = \text{Cap}_{j,t} + \sum_{i \in \text{NP}} \text{Cap}_i \text{repurp}_{i,t} + \sum_{j \in \text{RP}} \text{Create}_t \text{Add}_{j,t} + \sum_{j \in \text{RP}} \text{Cap}_{e,t} \text{Enhance}_{j,t}, \forall t \in T$$

Constraints

- Single Action per Non-Renewable Plant: $\sum_{t \in T} (C_{\text{decomm}}^{i,t} + C_{\text{repurp}}^{i,t}) \leq 1, \forall i \in \text{NP}$
- Non-negativity Constraint: $\sum_{t \in T} \text{Create}_j \geq 0, \forall j \in \text{RP}$
- Repurpose Once Constraint: $\sum_{t \in T} \text{repurp}_{i,t} \leq 1, \forall i \in \text{NP}$
- Mutual Exclusive (either enhance or create new): $(\text{Add}_{j,t} + \text{Enhance}_{j,t}) \leq 1, \forall t \in T$
- Renewable Capacity Limit: $C_{j,t} \leq \text{Cap}_j, \forall j \in \text{RP}, \forall t \in T$
- Non-Renewable Capacity Balance: $\text{Cap}_t \leq \text{Target}_n + s_t, \forall t \in T$
- Renewable Capacity Balance: $\text{Cap}_t \leq \text{Target} + s_t, \forall t \in T$
- Energy Demand Constraint: $\text{Cap}_t + \text{Cap}_t + s_t^d \geq (\text{Target}_n + \text{Target}), \forall t \in T$

These constraints ensure a structured transition toward sustainable energy targets while minimising costs and penalising deviations from planned capacities.

Standard Form of multi-step MIP

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{t \in T} \left(\sum_{i \in \text{NP}} C_{\text{decomm},i} \text{Cap}_i \text{decomm}_{i,t} + \sum_{i \in \text{NP}} C_{\text{repurpos},n} \text{Cap}_i \text{repurp}_{i,t} \right. \\ & \left. + C_{\text{create},t} + \sum_{j \in \text{RP}} C_{\text{build},j} \text{Cap}_{e,t} + p_t s_t + p_t s_t + p_t^d s_t^d \right) \end{aligned}$$

s.t.

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i \in I} (decomm_{i,t} + repurp_{i,t}) &\leq 1, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, p, \\
Add_{j,t} + E_{j,t} &\leq 1, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, q, \quad \forall t, \\
Cap_t - s_t &\leq Target_n, \quad \forall t, \\
Cap_t - s_t &\leq Target, \quad \forall t, \\
-(Cap_t + Cap_t + s_t^d) &\leq Target_n + Target, \quad \forall t, \\
Cap_{t+1} - Cap_t + \sum_{i \in NP} Cap_i (decomm_{i,t} + repurp_{i,t}) &= 0, \quad \forall t, \\
Cap_{j,t+1} - Cap_{j,t} - \sum_{i \in NP} Cap_i repurp_{i,t} - Create_t Add_{j,t} - Cap_{e,t} E_{j,t} &= 0, \quad \forall j, t, \\
decomm_{i,t}, repurp_{i,t}, Add_{j,t}, E_{j,t} &\in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall i, j, t, \\
Create_t, Cap_{e,t} &\in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}, \quad \forall t, \\
s_t, s_t, s_t^d &\geq 0, \quad \forall t.
\end{aligned}$$

5.2.1 Implementation

We implement our linear optimisation framework in the Python programming language and specifically the Pyomo open library [1, 5]. The linear programming solver is provided by the GNU Linear Programming Kit (GLPK) [14] (version 5.0). The problem is set up as a mixed integer problem within Pyomo, with the penalty decision variables as non-negative real numbers, and the rest of the decision variables as binary integers (0 or 1). Pyomo typically calls both the GLPK Integer Optimizer 5.0 and GLPK Simplex Optimizer 5.0 to provide a solution. The interested reader can find more details on the implementation in [this](#) repository.

5.3 Markov Decision Process

We aim to enhance the decision-making process for power system transitions by extending the traditional MIP model into a Markov Decision Process (MDP) framework. An MDP is a powerful mathematical formalism for modelling sequential decision-making under uncertainty, where actions taken in the current state influence both immediate outcomes and the probabilistic evolution of future states. This approach is particularly well-suited for dynamic and uncertain

environments—such as the transition of energy systems—where planning decisions must adapt to unpredictable changes in demand, technology, and regulation.

A key challenge in energy transition planning lies in managing uncertainty. These uncertainties arise from various sources: fluctuating energy demand (e.g., due to electric vehicle adoption), evolving regulatory environments, and rapid advances in renewable generation and storage technologies. By embedding these uncertainties within an MDP framework, we aim to develop more adaptive and resilient decision strategies that outperform static, deterministic models.

The MDP framework formalizes this sequential planning process through the tuple

$$(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, P, R, \gamma, T),$$

where:

- \mathcal{S} is the **state space**, representing the system’s status at each time step.
- \mathcal{A} is the **action space**, denoting all possible decisions available to the planner.
- $P(s' \mid s, a)$ is the **transition probability function**, capturing stochastic dynamics in state evolution.
- $R(s, a)$ is the **reward function**, quantifying the cost or benefit of taking action a in state s .
- $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ is the **discount factor**, which balances immediate and future outcomes.
- T is the **planning horizon**, representing the total number of decision epochs.

At each discrete time step $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$, the system resides in a state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$. The decision-maker selects an action $a_t \in \mathcal{A}(s_t)$, and the system transitions to a new state $s_{t+1} \sim P(\cdot \mid s_t, a_t)$ while receiving a reward $R(s_t, a_t)$. The objective is to find a policy $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ that maximizes the expected cumulative reward:

$$\max_{\pi} \mathbb{E}_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t R(s_t, a_t) \right].$$

The value function $V_t(s)$, representing the maximum expected return from state s

at time t , satisfies the Bellman recursion:

$$V_t(s) = \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \left[R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s' \in \mathcal{S}} P(s'|s, a) V_{t+1}(s') \right].$$

While this solution has not yet been implemented, its potential benefits are significant. A well-designed MDP framework would incorporate uncertainties that MIP ignores, providing decision makers with robust data-driven strategies to optimise infrastructure investments, mitigate risks, and ensure a transition to a sustainable energy system.

We now define each component of the MDP used in our model.

State Space (\mathcal{S})

At each time step t , the state of the system is represented as a tuple:

$$s_t = \left(\text{Cap}_t^n, \text{Cap}_t^r, \{D_i\}_{i=1}^p, \{R_i\}_{i=1}^p, \{B_j\}_{j=1}^q, \{E_j\}_{j=1}^q, s_t^n, s_t^r, s_t^d, D_t \right),$$

where Cap_t^n and Cap_t^r denote the discretized non-renewable and renewable capacities (MW), respectively. The binary indicators $D_i, R_i \in \{0, 1\}$ track whether non-renewable plant i has been decommissioned or repurposed, while $B_j, E_j \in \{0, 1\}$ indicate whether renewable plant j has been newly created or enhanced. Additionally, s_t^n, s_t^r, s_t^d represent slack variables measuring violations of capacity targets, and D_t corresponds to the discretized energy demand level (MW).

Action Space (\mathcal{A})

The decision-maker selects actions $a_t \in A$ at each time step, consisting of

- Non-renewable plant decisions: Each plant i can either remain operational, be decommissioned, or be repurposed, represented by $a_i \in \{0, \text{Decommission}, \text{Repurpose}\}$, subject to the constraint $D_i + R_i \leq 1$.
- Renewable capacity decisions: New renewable capacity may be introduced, denoted by $\text{Create}_t^r \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, while existing capacity can be enhanced, represented by $\text{Enhance}_t^r \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$. A mutual exclusivity constraint ensures that each renewable plant is either created or enhanced in a given time step: $B_{j,t}^r + E_{j,t}^r \leq 1$.

State Transition Dynamics ($P(s'|s, a)$)

State evolution incorporates both deterministic and stochastic components

- Deterministic capacity updates are governed by

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Cap}_{t+1}^n &= \text{Cap}_t^n - \sum_{i \in \text{NP}} \text{Cap}_i^n (D_{i,t} + R_{i,t}), \\ \text{Cap}_{t+1}^r &= \text{Cap}_t^r + \sum_{i \in \text{RP}} \text{Cap}_i^n R_{i,t} + \text{Create}_t^r + \text{Enhance}_t^r.\end{aligned}$$

- Stochastic demand evolution follows a Markov chain

$$D_{t+1} \sim P(D_{t+1}|D_t).$$

- Stochastic plant availability introduces random fluctuations in capacity, modelled as

$$\widetilde{\text{Cap}}_t^n = \text{Cap}_t^n \cdot \eta_t^n, \quad \widetilde{\text{Cap}}_t^r = \text{Cap}_t^r \cdot \eta_t^r,$$

where $\eta_t^n, \eta_t^r \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p)$ capture operational efficiency.

- Slack variable updates ensure adherence to capacity constraints

$$s_{t+1}^n = \max(0, \text{Cap}_t^n - \text{Target}_n), \quad \text{etc.}$$

Reward Function ($R(s, a)$)

The cost function is structured to penalise decommissioning, repurposing, and renewable expansion, as well as deviations from capacity targets

$$\begin{aligned}R(s_t, a_t) = - \left[\sum_{i \in \text{NP}} (C_n \cdot \text{Cap}_i^n D_{i,t} + C_{n2r} \cdot \text{Cap}_i^n R_{i,t}) \right. \\ \left. + C_r \cdot \text{Create}_t^r + C_{er} \cdot \text{Enhance}_t^r + p_t^n s_t^n + p_t^r s_t^r + p_t^d s_t^d \right].\end{aligned}$$

Planning Horizon and Discounting

The decision process spans a finite planning horizon

- Horizon: $T = 2050$ – start year.

- Discount factor: $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ balances immediate versus future costs.

Bellman Equation and Optimal Policy

The optimal value function $V_t(s)$ satisfies the Bellman recursion

$$V_t(s) = \max_{a \in A} \left[R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) V_{t+1}(s') \right],$$

with terminal condition $V_T(s) = 0$. The objective is to minimize the expected total cost over the planning horizon:

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=1}^T \gamma^{t-1} R(s_t, a_t) \right].$$

The transition probabilities decompose as

$$P(s'|s, a) = P(D_{t+1}|D_t) \cdot P(\eta_t^n) \cdot P(\eta_t^r).$$

This formulation captures key aspects of energy planning, aligning with the structure and objectives of existing MIP frameworks while incorporating uncertainty through the MDP framework.

6 Results and Discussions

Our method consistently found a viable solution regardless of the scenario or the number of power plants involved. The approach successfully navigated key constraints, including minimising total demand deficits, reducing excess non-renewable capacity, and ensuring the minimum required renewable generation was met according to each scenario. This confirms that the model performs effectively within the given constraints and works under different scenarios while ensuring the energy transition remains feasible within the problem's defined limits. Moreover, by employing linear optimisation, this method establishes a robust baseline for evaluating more advanced approaches that may further enhance the transition pathways.

6.1 Clockwork Scenario

In the Clockwork scenario, the impact of project limitations on the energy transition is significant. When unlimited interventions (see Figure 2 and Figure 4a) are allowed, the optimiser aggressively decommissions all coal and oil plants by 2025, rapidly replacing them with large-scale wind energy deployment. This results in a sharp capacity increase from 80 GW to 90 GW; however, it follows an unrealistic implementation pathway due to infrastructure and supply chain constraints, with the transition occurring too rapidly.

In contrast, with limited interventions (see Figure 3 and Figure 4b), the transition unfolds without being able to closely meet all the milestones. The initial years (2025–2035) focus on gradual fossil fuel decommissioning and repurposing, followed by enhancements to existing infrastructure and the expansion of nuclear energy. Only in the later stages (2045–2050) do large offshore wind developments emerge, aligning more closely with real-world deployment timelines. However, this constraint is too restrictive, leading to an initial capacity decline and an unmet energy demand by 2050. This suggests that more active projects are needed per period to meet net zero goals, and the number of those projects should require further fine-tuning to balance practical deployment rates with the urgency of net zero targets.

Figure 2: Generation capacity compared to required capacity in the Clockwork scenario with unlimited interventions (1000 work years per period).

Figure 3: Generation capacity compared to required capacity in the Clockwork scenario with limited interventions (50 work years per period).

(a) Without intervention limits

(b) With intervention limits

Figure 4: Power plant actions in the Clockwork scenario

6.2 Patchwork Scenario

A similar dynamic emerges in the Patchwork scenario, where project limitations also play a critical role in shaping the transition's feasibility. Under unlimited interventions (see Figure 5 and Figure 7a), the initial phase (2025) sees widespread fossil fuel decommissioning and a rapid expansion of both onshore and offshore wind projects. However, unlike Clockwork, where challenges occur primarily at the beginning, Patchwork experiences a second wave of interventions between 2045 and 2050. This late-stage acceleration is driven by a sharp increase in offshore wind energy demand, leading the optimiser to concentrate deployments in the final years. While this ensures energy demand is met, it creates challenges similar to Clockwork, particularly regarding supply chain and infrastructure capacity. However, in Patchwork, these issues arise at two critical points instead of just one, necessitating effective coordination both at the start and toward the end of the transition to prevent bottlenecks.

When interventions are limited to 50 work years worth of projects per step, the transition follows a more evenly distributed trajectory (see Figure 6 and Figure 7b). The early years (2025–2035) prioritise upgrading existing infrastructure and repurposing fossil fuel plants, with new nuclear power plants introduced in the first two stages. From 2035 onward, offshore wind deployment gradually increases to accommodate growing demand, beginning earlier than in the unlimited projects case (2035 vs. 2045) to compensate for the restricted intervention capacity. However, by 2050, energy demand is still not fully met, and non-renewable power plants are not fully decommissioned. As in Clockwork, this outcome highlights the limitations of a highly constrained intervention strategy. More active projects per period are needed, along with further adjustments to balance practical deployment rates with the urgency of reaching net zero.

Figure 5: Generation capacity compared to required capacity in the Patchwork scenario with unlimited interventions (1000 work years per period).

Figure 6: Generation capacity compared to required capacity in the Patchwork scenario with limited interventions (50 work years per period).

(a) Without intervention limits

(b) With intervention limits

Figure 7: Power plant actions over time in the Patchwork scenario

6.3 Discussion

This study presents an optimisation-based framework for managing the UK's energy transition, ensuring a balance between decommissioning fossil fuel power plants, repurposing existing infrastructure, and scaling up renewable energy sources. The model successfully finds viable pathways across different transition scenarios while adhering to key constraints: minimising energy demand deficits, reducing excess non-renewable capacity, and ensuring that minimum renewable energy targets are met.

By leveraging linear optimisation, this approach provides a clear and structured decision-making tool that can guide long-term energy planning. While it simplifies some of the real-world complexities, such as supply chain constraints and evolving policy landscapes, it serves as a strong baseline for evaluating more advanced models. Policymakers can use these insights to refine intervention strategies, ensuring that infrastructure and workforce capabilities align with the pace of the energy transition.

The results highlight the importance of balancing ambition with practicality as overly aggressive transitions can strain resources, while overly restrictive intervention limits may delay critical progress toward Net Zero. Future research can explore more sophisticated optimisation techniques, incorporating uncertainty and real-time adjustments to better reflect the dynamic nature of energy markets and technological advancements.

Ultimately, this work confirms that a structured, data-driven approach can help policymakers navigate the complexities of energy transition, ensuring that Net Zero targets are met efficiently and realistically.

6.3.1 Limitations

The application of a MIP approach to capacity planning for renewable and non-renewable energy sources presents several limitations. Computational complexity increases as the number of time periods and decision variables grows, all MIP optimisations in this report run in reasonable times, but this has to be considered before starting a more detailed study considering more periods and more power plants.

MIP assumes deterministic inputs, whereas real-world energy planning is subject to uncertainties in energy demand, cost fluctuations, and policy changes. While

incorporating stochastic or robust optimisation can address these uncertainties, it further amplifies computational costs. Additionally, the multi-step structure of the model imposes strong sequential dependencies among decisions, and linear optimisation or other static methods restrict flexibility in responding to unforeseen changes over time. Finally, solver performance is highly sensitive to formulation quality and parameter tuning, and in some cases, heuristic or reinforcement learning-based approaches may offer more scalable alternatives. These challenges underscore the trade-offs between model accuracy and computational feasibility in long-term energy planning.

7 Conclusion

We have proposed and implemented a mixed integer linear optimisation framework to achieve a transition to net zero energy production by 2050. The current framework takes as input data from an ESME decarbonisation scenario and proposes actions on the power plants given by the JRC dataset, to achieve this transition at minimal financial cost. Scenario energy demands are encoded as soft constraints, with associated penalties for unmet targets. These penalties are given as hyperparameters in our framework, together with the work hours that can be spent per time step, in order to follow the desired scenario.

For the cases we studied, we found that the framework always provided a solution to the problem, which depends on the values of the hyper-parameters. For given penalties, we see that the tuning of the work hours provides sensible results, with unlimited resources leading to numerous early-stage actions, and limited ones spreading them more evenly over time. The quality of the solution depends on the data available, some of which has been estimated in this study (e.g. intervention duration, transition costs). This linear optimisation framework provides a baseline for this problem, it might be enhanced by incorporating more decision variables or improving the quality of the input data.

7.1 Future Work

There are more meaningful explorations that can be made with the current state of the framework, for instance, investigating the effect of the penalties on the solution for fixed work hours, or attempting to find a solution that can optimise both clockwork and patchwork scenarios simultaneously (via robust optimisation

techniques). Another possible direction is to expand on the decision variables (e.g. allow for more actions per plant over time, currently we assume only one action per plant), or the constraints (for example also enforce that there is not a big excess of renewable capacity as well).

Also, during this work, we solely consider capacity; however, more measures such as energy generation or seasonal details should be taken into account for a more detailed analysis.

A promising extension involves integrating **Markov Decision Processes (MDPs)** to handle sequential decision-making under uncertainty. While our mixed-integer programming (MIP) approach yields optimal static plans under deterministic assumptions, MDPs allow the system to react adaptively to evolving scenarios—such as changes in policy, costs, or energy demand by defining probabilistic transitions between states.

Future steps include designing interpretable state spaces (e.g., based on capacity, cost, and resource constraints), modelling stochastic transitions, and testing reinforcement learning approaches such as value iteration. These improvements would significantly enhance the realism and flexibility of our model for real-world energy transition planning.

Code Availability

The code used for this study is available at [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14996335) (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14996335](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14996335)).

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Team members

Giovanni Briglia is a PhD student at the University of Pisa specialising in Causal Reinforcement Learning. He received both MSc and Bsc in Robotics Engineering at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. He contributed to this project by taking care of data management and preparation. He also contributed to the implementation of the optimiser and the visualization of the results.

Thanasis Giannakopoulos is a postdoctoral research fellow at the University of Nottingham, specialised in numerical relativity. His contribution on this project was on the data analysis and pre-processing, the coding of the optimisation problem, and the visualization.

Sokipriala Jonah Is a PhD student at the Centre for Computational Science and Mathematical Modelling, Coventry University, his research focuses on the optimisation of cyber-physical systems. He co-facilitated this challenge, contributing to the mathematical formulation and developing the coding pipeline with the Pyomo optimiser

Zhaoxing Li is a Research Fellow at the University of Southampton. He received his PhD in Artificial Intelligence at Durham University in 2023. His research focuses on making AI more accessible to citizens, enabling broader engagement and interaction. His interests include citizen-centric AI, deep learning, reinforcement learning, multi-agent systems, and large language models. He contributed to the project by developing the mathematical formulation.

Taha Sajjad has recently done PhD. in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science from York University Canada. She is pursuing a postdoc in the application of machine learning in nano communications networks and the Internet of Things

(IoT). She has contributed to the project by defining the framework of problem and mathematical formulation.

Lydia Tsiami is a researcher at KWR Water Research Institute in the Netherlands and a PhD student in Civil Engineering at NTUA in Greece. She specializes in hydroinformatics, applying Machine Learning to hydraulic engineering and water management. In this project, she worked on analyzing the dataset, formulating the optimisation problem, and designing the experimental setup. She also contributed to the development and coding of the framework.

Congye Wang is a PhD student in Mathematics at Newcastle University. His research primarily concentrates on computational statistics and probabilistic machine learning. His contributions to this project include developing the mathematical formulation.

Zining Yuan is a PhD student in Climate Finance at King's College London. Her research interests are Climate Finance, Risk and Uncertainty, and the linkage between macro-finance and climate change. She is the co-facilitator for this challenge. She also contributed to the project by developing the mathematical method and providing insights to net zero.

Oluwatosin Uthman Zubair is an Electrical and Electronics Engineer with over four years of progressive experience in the oil and gas, EPC, and power industries. He specializes in renewable and non-renewable energy systems, electrical system design, BOQ preparation, and SLD creation using AutoCAD, along with developing technical and commercial proposals. Currently, he is pursuing a PhD in Business Analytics at the University of Hertfordshire, focusing on Cost Analysis of Digital Twin in Building Energies. His contributions to this project include cost analysis and providing technical insights to support the project's success.

Tereso del Río holds a PhD in Computer Algebra and Machine Learning from Coventry University. His doctoral research focuses on the integration of machine learning into cylindrical algebraic decomposition. Currently, he is interested in employing operational research methods to improve real-world processes. He served as the Principal Investigator in this challenge.

A Technologies in ESME Scenarios

Technology	Clockwork	Patchwork
Hydrogen Micro Cogeneration - Space Heat		✓
Interconnector Benelux-Germany (Electricity)	✓	✓
Interconnector France (Electricity)	✓	✓
Interconnector Ireland (Electricity)	✓	✓
Interconnector Nordel (Electricity)	✓	✓
Oil Fired Generation	✓	✓
Gas Macro Cogeneration	✓	✓
Open Cycle Gas Turbine	✓	✓
Pulverized Coal	✓	✓
Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle Coal with Carbon Capture and Storage - 99% Carbon Capture Rate	✓	
Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle Coal with Carbon Capture and Storage		✓
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine	✓	✓
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine with Carbon Capture and Storage	✓	✓
Combined Cycle Gas Turbine with Carbon Capture and Storage - 99% Carbon Capture Rate	✓	
Waste Gasification	✓	✓
Waste Gasification with Carbon Capture and Storage	✓	✓

Nuclear (Legacy)	✓	✓
Nuclear (Gen III)	✓	✓
Nuclear (Gen IV)		✓
Small Modular Reactor Cogeneration	✓	
Small Modular Reactor Cogeneration (NE)		✓
Small Modular Reactor Cogeneration (NW)		✓
Small Modular Reactor Cogeneration (SW)		✓
Small Modular Reactor Electricity Only		✓
Biomass Fired Generation	✓	✓
Converted Biomass Plant (Drax)	✓	✓
Biomass Macro Cogeneration		✓
Integrated Gasification Combined Cycle Biomass with Carbon Capture and Storage		✓
Incineration of Waste	✓	✓
Anaerobic Digestion Cogeneration Plant	✓	✓
Hydrogen Turbine	✓	✓
Onshore Wind	✓	✓
Offshore Wind (Fixed)	✓	✓
Offshore Wind (Floating)	✓	✓
Solar Photovoltaics (Farm)	✓	✓
Solar Photovoltaics (Domestic)	✓	✓
Hydro Power	✓	✓

Tidal Stream	✓	✓
Geothermal Plant (EGS) Electricity		✓

Table 8: Technologies of ESME Scenarios in Clockwork and Patchwork Models

B List of actions

Under the patchwork scenario and with 50 work years per period, the following roadmap was designed by our tool:

Table 9: Power Plant Actions: EIC Code, Generation Type, Action, and Year

Identification	Type	Action	Year
48WSTN0000HINB5	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000HUNBV	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000ABTHBN	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Biomass	2025
48WSTN0000EGGPS5	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000FIDL	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000HEYM1P	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000RATS9	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000DRAXXK	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000WBUPSE	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
nuclear_0	New Build	Built Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000GRGBW9	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2025
48WSTN0000LARYWP	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2025
48WSTN0000TORN	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000SIZBP	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000HRTL5	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000DNGBQ	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN1000COTPSQ	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000HEYM2N	Nuclear	Enhanced Nuclear	2025
48WSTN0000WDNSOV	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
48WSTN0000RCBKOV	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
48WSTN0000WLN	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
48WSTN0000RMPNON	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
48WSTN0000GYMRWD	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
48WSTN0000WLN	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030
nuclear_3	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
48WSTN0000IRNPS9	Fossil Hard coal	Repurposed Coal to Nuclear	2030
48WSTN0000WLN	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2030

Continued on next page

Table 9: Power Plant Actions

Identification	Type	Action	Year
nuclear_7	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
nuclear_6	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
nuclear_5	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
48WSTN1000WHILWQ	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2030
48WSTN0000WDNSWF	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2030
nuclear_4	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
48WSTN00000CRUAC	Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	Enhanced Hydro River	2030
nuclear_1	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
nuclear_2	New Build	Built Nuclear	2030
48WSTN00000FOYEQ	Hydro Run-of-river and poundage	Enhanced Hydro River	2035
wind_off_124	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_13	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_126	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_125	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_123	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
48WSTN0000BRBEOT	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_127	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
48WSTN0000STLGW3	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2035
48WSTN0000HMGTOR	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2035
48WSTN0000SHRSW3	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2035
48WSTN0000PNYCWB	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2035
48WSTN0000WTMSOT	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2035
48WSTN0000KLGW3	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2035
48WSTN0000GRIFWQ	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2035
48WSTN0000THNTOQ	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2035
47W00000000156I	Fossil Oil	Repurposed Oil to Biomass	2035
47W00000000153O	Fossil Oil	Repurposed Oil to Biomass	2035
wind_off_129	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_99	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_128	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_130	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2035
wind_off_100	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_11	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_14	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_132	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_110	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_111	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
48WSTN0000PEMBL	Fossil Gas	Decommissioned Gas	2040
wind_off_139	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040

Continued on next page

Table 9: Power Plant Actions

Identification	Type	Action	Year
48WSTN0000CRYRBT	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2040
wind_off_153	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_152	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_144	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_143	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_142	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_141	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_140	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_138	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_10	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2040
wind_off_135	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
48WSTN0000OMNDWQ	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_15	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_112	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
48WSTN0000GNFSWJ	Wind Offshore	Enhanced Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_136	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_131	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_150	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_137	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_133	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_145	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_146	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_147	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_148	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_149	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_151	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_122	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_134	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2045
wind_off_115	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_155	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_154	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_12	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_121	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_159	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_120	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_119	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_118	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_158	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_117	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050

Continued on next page

Table 9: Power Plant Actions

Identification	Type	Action	Year
48WSTN0000FAARW2	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2050
48WSTN0000FALGWS	Wind Onshore	Enhanced Wind Onshore	2050
wind_off_157	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_116	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_16	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_114	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050
wind_off_156	New Build	Built Wind Offshore	2050

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